

3D Morphological and Volumetric Assessment of the Sella Turcica on CT Scans: A Comparative Study of Males and Females in Jos, North Central Nigeria

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Abstract

Introduction: Sella turcica (ST) is a saddle-shaped middle cranial fossa structure that constitutes a significant landmark when imaging the brain and the base of the skull.

Objective: This study aimed to analyze and compare the morphological and volumetric characteristics of sella turcica on three-dimensional (3D) Computed Tomography (CT) Scan in males and female.

Methodology: This is a retrospective comparative study of 200 brain scans done at a private medical diagnostics center in Jos, North Central Nigeria. 3D CT Images of the sella turcica on bone window were obtained from adult patients without discrimination of gender from the database of the diagnostic center. Patients with history of cranial trauma, surgery or pathological conditions affecting the sella turcica are excluded. Measurements of the sella turcica's dimensions (length, width and depth) using digital calipers were obtained. The sella turcica's volume is calculated using Di Chiro-Nelson method [$0.5 \times (\text{length} \times \text{width} \times \text{depth})$]

Results: The majority of the participants were males 118 (59%) with a mean age of 48.3 ± 18.1 years while the female patients were 82 (41%) with a mean age of 47.4 ± 17.6 years. The overall mean length, width, depth and volume of the sella turcica were 12.46 mm, 13.24 mm, 8.39mm and 702.03 mm³ for males and 11.90 mm, 13.31 mm, 8.77mm and 703.71 mm³ for females respectively. A greater number of the participants have normal variant sella turcica 89 (44.5%), followed distantly by the oblique anterior wall 40 (20%) while the list seen is the irregularity of posterior wall which accounts for 6 (3.0%).

Conclusion: The study revealed a slight variation in the mean length, depth, width and volume of ST in males and females in our environment. The dominant ST type was the normal variant which is consistent with most of the studies reviewed.

More Information

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Introduction

The sella turcica is a distinct anatomical feature situated within the middle cranial fossa and serves as the bony enclosure for the pituitary gland. This saddle-shaped depression is bordered by the anterior and posterior clinoid processes, with the hypophyseal fossa located centrally. The hypophyseal fossa, which contains the pituitary gland, is in close proximity to numerous anatomically and functionally significant structures [1,2].

Historically, the sella turcica was categorized into three morphological types: circular, oval, and flattened or saucer-like, with most individuals exhibiting either circular or oval forms. More recently, its classification has expanded to six primary morphological types: normal sella turcica, oblique anterior wall, double-contoured sella, posterior wall irregularity (notching), pyramidal dorsum sellae, and sella turcica bridging [2,20].

The pituitary gland, located at the deepest part of the sella turcica, plays a vital role as the master endocrine organ, orchestrating the regulation of various hormonal functions throughout the body. Numerous pathological and developmental conditions can lead to changes in the size of the pituitary gland, which, in turn, may influence the dimensions and structure of the sella turcica due to their interconnected growth and development [3,4].

Notably, the shape and volume of the sella turcica can differ significantly among individuals, both with and without pituitary disorders. Because the morphology of the sella turcica often mirrors that of the pituitary gland, its measurements hold diagnostic relevance. Studies conducted across diverse populations have reported variations in the size and volume of the sella turcica [5].

Contemporary imaging modalities—such as digital radiography, computed tomography (CT), and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)—are widely employed for detailed assessment of the sella turcica. CT scans, in particular, are tailored for imaging the craniofacial skeleton and offer three-dimensional visualization of the targeted area.

This study aims to evaluate sex-based differences in sella turcica morphology by analyzing its shape and dimensions using cephalometric techniques.

Materials and Methods

A retrospective, comparative study was conducted, utilizing CT scans from a sample of 200 Nigerian individuals (comprising 108 males and 58 females) who underwent brain CT imaging at a private

radiodiagnostic facility in Jos, located in North Central Nigeria. Data collection involved retrieving archived CT images after obtaining the necessary permissions from the relevant authorities, with no restrictions based on age or sex. Subjects with a history of skull base fractures, tumors, surgical interventions, or congenital structural anomalies were excluded from the study.

All sella turcica images were captured using a Siemens Somatom Sensation 64-slice CT scanner. The acquired data were subsequently processed and analyzed on a Work Station AW Volume Share2 platform, employing multiplanar reformatting techniques, maximum intensity projection, and volume rendering.

The following measurements were taken: (1) ST length—measured as the distance from the tuberculum sellae to the dorsum sellae; (2) ST width—defined as the distance between the two lateral walls of the sella turcica at their midpoint; and (3) ST depth—measured from the line of the length to the deepest point of the hypophyseal fossa.

The volume of the sella turcica was calculated using the Di Chiro-Nelson formula: $0.5 \times (\text{length} \times \text{width} \times \text{depth})$ [6].

Morphological assessment of the sella turcica was conducted by observing the lateral view of the skull scanogram, focusing specifically on the sella turcica. The shapes were categorized according to six modified classifications: (1) normal sella turcica; (2) oblique anterior wall; (3) double-contoured sella; (4) irregularity (notching) in the posterior sella; (5) pyramidal dorsum sellae; and (6) sella turcica bridge.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS software (version 25.0, IBM Corp., Chicago, IL, USA, 2017). Continuous variables were reported as means (\bar{x}) and standard deviations (SD). Morphological and volumetric differences of the sella turcica between male and female subjects were evaluated. Associations between variables were assessed using the Chi-square test. Results were presented in appropriate tabular formats. Statistical significance was determined at a p-value of ≤ 0.05 , with a 95% confidence interval 21.

Age and Sex Distribution

A total of 200 Brain CT scanned images was included in the study. The majority of the participants were males 118 (59%) with a mean age of 48.3 ± 18.1 years while the female patients were 82(41%) with a mean age of 47.4 ± 17.6 years. Higher proportions of both male (22.0%) and female (25.6%) patients were between 41-50 years. The difference was not statistically significant ($t = 0.748, p = 0.827$) (see Table 1).

Table 1: Age and Sex Distribution of Patients

Age group (years)	Sex			χ^2 /t-test	p-value
	Male	Female	Total		
11-20	9(7.6)	8(9.8)	17(8.5)		

21-30	14(11.9)	9(11.0)	23(11.5)		
31-40	20(16.9)	9(11.0)	29(14.5)		
41-50	26(22.0)	21(25.6)	47(23.5)		
51-60	19(16.1)	15(18.3)	34(17.0)		
61-70	11(9.3)	11(13.4)	22(11.0)		
71-80	17(14.4)	8(9.8)	25(12.5)		
81-90	2(1.7)	1(1.2)	3(1.5)		
Total	118(100.0)	82(100.0)	200(100.0)	3.528	0.832
Mean± SD	48.3±18.1	47.4±17.6	47.9±17.9	0.748	0.827

Results

Sella Turcica Type

The study showed that 89(44.5%) patients had Normal Sella Turcica with 52(44.1%) males and 37(45.1%) of females. For the Oblique Anterior wall sella turcica Type, 30(25.4%) and 10(12.2%) were seen in males and females respectively. On the other hand, 19(16.1%) males had Double Contour Floor which is proportionally

lower than it was found among female patients (23.2%). There were only 2(1.7%) of males and 4(4.9%) of female who had Irregularity of Posterior wall while 10 (8.5%) of males and 5(6.1%) of females had Pyramidal shape of dorsum sellae. Sella turcica bridge was higher 7(8.5%) in females than it was in males (4.2). This difference in proportion was not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 9.007, p = 0.10$) (see Table 2).

Table 2: Sella Turcica Type

Sella Type	Sex			χ^2	p-value
	Male	Female	Total		
Normal	52(44.1)	37(45.1)	89(44.5)		
Oblique anterior wall	30(25.4)	10(12.2)	40(20.0)		
Double contour floor	19(16.1)	19(23.2)	38(19.0)		
Irregularity of posterior wall	2(1.7)	4(4.9)	6(3.0)		
Pyramidal shape of dorsum sellae	10(8.5)	5(6.1)	15(7.5)		
Sella Turcica bridge	5(4.2)	7(8.5)	12(6.0)		
Total	118(100.0)	82(100.0)	200(100.0)	9.007	0.109

Sella Turcica Features

The mean ST length was higher in male patients (12.46±1.94cm) than the female patients (11.90±1.75cm) (t = 2.079, p = 0.039).

Conversely, ST width, depth and volume were higher among female patients than the male patients with 13.31±1.83 vs 13.24±1.98, 8.77±1.56 vs 8.39±1.58 and 703.71±227.40 vs 702.03±240.50 respectively. (p>0.05) (see Table 3).

Table 3: Sella Turcica Features

Properties	Male Mean± SD	Female Mean± SD	T	p-value
ST Length	12.46±1.94	11.90±1.75	2.079	0.039
ST Width	13.24±1.98	13.31±1.83	-0.253	0.801
ST Depth	8.39±1.58	8.77±1.56	-1.681	0.094
ST Volume	702.03±240.50	703.71±227.40	-0.049	0.961

Discussion

The sella turcica is a saddle-like depression found in the sphenoid bone within the middle cranial fossa, serving as the cavity for the pituitary gland. Alterations in its shape and volume may arise due to congenital defects or pathological conditions affecting either the pituitary gland itself or adjacent anatomical structures [7,8]. Assessing the typical dimensions, forms, and volume of the sella turcica plays a crucial role in identifying and investigating abnormalities that could indicate underlying diseases.

The globally reported normal values for sella turcica dimensions vary, depending on the location and technique of measurement. On average, the value range for ST length is between 10 mm and 16 mm, the ST depth from 8 mm to 12 mm, and the ST width from 10mm to 15mm [9,10,11]. Our study revealed a mean ST length of 12.18mm±1.85 with a slightly higher mean value in males when compared with the females (12.46mm±1.94 vs 11.90mm±1.75). [12] and [13] in their separate studies also recorded slightly higher values in males when compared with females in a Saudi

population (11.0mm vs 10.6mm) and an Indian population (9.04mm vs 8.46mm). [14] in their study in Khartoum, Sudan, recorded a slightly higher mean ST length value in females when compared with their male counterparts (8.65 vs 8.01). Although our ST length values fall within the globally documented range, they are, however, comparably higher when compared with the mean values recorded by [4] (10.11mm), [5] (10.8mm), [14] (8.33mm) and [15] (9.73mm) in their studies, but comparable with those reported by [16] (12.4mm) and [17] (12.59mm) in Sokoto and Port Harcourt in North west and south-south Nigeria respectively. The analysis of variance test showed that there was a statistically significant difference in ST length with gender, where the p-value was 0.039.

The mean ST depth was shown to be slightly higher in the female participants than the male counterparts in our study. [11] and [18] also recorded a higher value of ST width in females when compared to males in their studies in Jordan and Ethiopia respectively. Although our study documented a higher value in females, the overall values are relatively higher compared with those reported by [11], [16] and [18], and recorded in the separate studies.

The mean ST width value in the current study appears to be lower compared with similar studies in Nigeria, Ethiopia and Jordan [11,16,18].

The discrepancies in findings could be attributed to the application of varying measurement methods or the selection of different anatomical landmarks for defining precise dimensions.

Regarding the variation in the anatomical shapes of the sella turcica, we found the following mean values: Normal variant (44.5%) followed by oblique anterior wall (20.0%) and the least common founding is the irregularity of posterior wall which accounts for (3.0%). When comparing according to the genders of the participants, the normal variant, double contour floor, irregularity of posterior wall, and sella turcica bridge types are observed to be slightly higher in females than their male counterparts. Our findings, which show the normal variant as the common shape, followed by oblique anterior wall are similar to those reported by [13] and [16] in their respective studies. However, Alkofide et al reported the oblique anterior as the most common, followed by the normal variant.

The results of this study revealed no significant difference in the mean values for ST volume between male and female participants. Our mean value of 703.71 ± 227.40 for female's vs 702.03 ± 240.50 for males are significantly higher than those reported by [4] (476.1 ± 132.4 vs 523.8 ± 186.0) and [14] (329.14 ± 206 vs 354.78 ± 199) reported in their studies but much lower than the mean value documented by [8] (951.3 ± 278.5 vs 1102.0 ± 285.3). This finding is not

concomitants with earlier published works that reported significant differences in the volumes.

The outcome of our current study has shown great similarities with studies done by [2] in Indian, Usman et al also in Nigerian and [19] in Iraq, where gender showed little effect on the mean value of ST length, depth, width and volume.

Conclusion

Our study shows no significant differences in the dimensions and volume of volume of ST in males and females in our environment. The dominant ST type was the normal variant followed distantly by the Oblique anterior wall type.

limitations

Landmarks for measurements were difficult in some cases due to the patient head orientation or positioning.

Conflict of Interests

We declare to have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. We the authors declare that we have no conflict of interest.

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